

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Berowa, I. N. E. (2024). The Vertical Integration Model of Peacebuilding as Applied to the Bangsamoro Peace Process. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 7(3), 202-215.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.07.03.516

The online version of this article can be found at:

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Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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The Vertical Integration Model of Peacebuilding as Applied to the Bangsamoro Peace Process

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to apply the vertical integration framework to the Bangsamoro peace process. The model can be applied to the Bangsamoro peace process through an inspection of the actors involved in the process: mediation, facilitation, and implementation. However, given the multitude of actors involved in the triple nexus of peacebuilding, it entails cooperation, coordination, and collaboration based on mutual trust and a multitude of other factors. Participation and accommodation are just features of the peace process since what matters most is the realization that possible solutions may just be around the corner which can be achieved through indigenous processes already known to the locals themselves.

Keywords: Bangsamoro Peace Process, Vertical Integration Model, The Local

1. Introduction

The Bangsamoro peace process is an ongoing liberal project. Various administrations have initiated in one way or another, with the assistance of foreign governments, transnational civil society groups, and local civil society organizations, to institute peace in the Bangsamoro homeland, yet peace is still elusive. Until today, packets of resistance from rebel groups, such as the Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighters (BIFF), the Abu Sayyaf, and extreme fundamentalists inspired by the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS), the Maute-ISIS, still threaten the fragile illusion of peace in Mindanao, notwithstanding the prolonged communist insurgency in other parts of the country. History points to the injustices suffered by the Bangsamoro for decades since the inception of Philippine Independence as the root cause of the problem. However, massive efforts to address this have been instituted from the Tripoli Agreement in 1976 to the 1996 Final Peace Agreement establishing the now defunct Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM), to the 2014 Comprehensive Agreement on Bangsamoro (CAB), to the signing of the Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL) in 2018, and the institutionalization of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) on March 2019 have been equally remarkable, yet the Bangsamoro peace process is yet to produce lasting peace (Kingston, 2019).

International norms dictate that states embrace democratic values, yet the rights regime also espouse the right of indigenous communities to self-determination. Both of these have been utilized as causes by leaders of Muslim

rebels to call for greater autonomy through armed struggle. On one hand, secularism is not an option in Islamic governance because the Western liberal concept of the separation of church and state is alien to the teachings of the Holy Qur'an. It requires that only those who are devout of the faith and have memorized the provisions of the holy book (*hafiz*) as well as in possession of the depth of understanding of the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad (Peace be upon Him), can be elected as Islamic leaders. Hence, democracy is not antithetical to Islam, as Islamic practice allows for a qualified system of consultation (*mushawir*) and the election of Islamic leaders, to ensure that leaders thus elected would not veer away from Islamic tenets, dogma and values. This is of course, ideally, with the assistance of a consultative council (*Majlis*) or *Shura* council. An imperfect example of this system is that of the 'revolution from above' of rentier states where women are *appointed* (instead of being *elected* as in a democracy) as members of the *Shura* councils in the Middle East, although yet qualifying that oil is at fault (Ross, 2008) for the democratic deficit, not Islam. On the other hand, greater autonomy resulted from legalizing the Bangsamoro peace process (Carolan, 2016) with the series of agreements signed between the rebels and the government peace panel – with the MNLF in the 1976 and 1996, with the MILF in 2008 (declared as unconstitutional by the Supreme Court), and again with the 2014 CAB and 2019 Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL) that paved the way for the current BARMM. Apparently, peace agreements can be enhanced by their incorporation into domestic law and through international oversight mechanisms (Ozcelik, 2020).

Peacebuilding is a process that needs the convergence of international, national and local peace initiatives to work towards the progress of attaining lasting peace. The global agenda under the triple nexus of humanitarian-development-peace nexus has ushered humanitarian, development, and peacebuilding actors to come to the aid of conflict-affected populations, ensuring inclusivity and the development of local ownership such that peace would be made sustainable. However, given the protracted peace process with the Bangsamoro, and with the belligerent communist insurgency and some packets of Islamic extremists in the countryside, the present paper endeavors to investigate the vertical integration model of peacebuilding and how this is applied to the peace process.

1.1 Review of Related Literature

1.1.1 Peacebuilding and the vertical integration framework

A vertical integration perspective points to the importance of long-term consensus building among all key constituencies involved in postconflict transitions around both the means and ends of peace-building processes, through participatory processes that neither co-opt the agency of the less powerful actors nor close off opportunities for different perspectives to emerge (Donais & McCandless, 2017). A vertical integration refers to strategies that link actors, knowledge, and processes upwards a cross societal strata for improved peacebuilding and development (Gray & Burns, 2021). This entails the combination of local civil society actor's knowledge of context and access to conflict-affected locations, with the expertise and generous funding of international actors and their capacity to connect the international to the national. According to a recent research, context-specific approaches highlight the importance of local agencies for peacebuilding to become more sustainable within the broader spectrum of the peace process (Muto & Saraiva, 2020).

Vertical relationships between local and nation, as well as international, levels and actors are of importance for peacebuilding as they are critical to developments occurring on the ground (Leonardsson, 2020). The research stresses that the concept of vertical relationships implies relationships across levels of governance but also incorporate space for interconnections that move freely across levels and scales, including relationships with individual actors or non-state organizations related to another government level or spatial scales, such as national politicians or experts in the field. In addition, these vertical relationships must be complementary and mutually reinforcing. However, a much earlier work (McCandless, Abitbol & Donais, 2015) already provided a clear definition of vertical integration, positing that at the most basic level, is a strategy to link actors, ideas and efforts vertically for peacebuilding and development impact. This requires that the dynamics of locally-led initiatives of peacebuilding must be vertically integrated to the dynamism of the international and the national, hence, it is considered as a concerted effort of various actors that transcend the silos of the humanitarian-peace-development nexus as well as that barriers of agency of the local, national and the international. The authors further assert that

minimum conditions for vertical integration efforts to gain traction include the existence of political space and the willingness of the governments of fragile and conflict-affected states to engage.

1.1.2 Situating the local

An analysis of the concept of localization across the three parts of the triple nexus – humanitarian, development, and peace - was the subject of a recent research (Barakat & Milton, 2020) since localization is a central issue on the international humanitarian agenda. The authors traced the concern of the local in each of these domains and proceeded to frame the challenges common to localization across the forms of conflict response: defining the local, valuing local capacity, maintaining political will, and multi-scalar conflict response. The authors posit that the Triple Nexus, proposed by UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres in 2017, could enable the breaking down of the silos of the humanitarian, development, and peacebuilding sectors. The trend towards localization is primarily driven by the value of local actors in terms of more effective humanitarian operations due to their local knowledge appropriate for their culture and context, in short, they are at the frontlines of the humanitarian response to crisis situations. The author also adds that the concept of localization in humanitarian action differs from that of peacebuilding and development because the humanitarian system is more centralized and streamlined globally. In this research, the local is considered as a relational concept dealing with power relations between the local and the international, the local and the regional, or the local and the national. Nonetheless, the authors assert that localization should be primarily about empowerment and effectiveness.

However, to avoid the abovementioned binaries of power – local versus international, the local versus the regional, or the local versus the national - the local should be seen as a sphere of activity, a system of beliefs and practices that loose communities and networks may adopt such that peacebuilding is enabled without reference to any specific place (Mac Ginty, 2015). Hence, the author asserts that the local is not a place. Rather, it is a concept that is de-territorialized, networked and constituted by people and activity (Mac Ginty, 2015). For him, to see this version of the local, we need to pay attention to context-specific knowledge that are concomitant constructions by the local and the global and the multitude of points in between.

In the same vein, the construction of the local and the international as binary opposites was a core problem in the literature on the local turn (Paffenholz, 2015). The author argues that this construction is at the heart of many problems and contradictions: (1) the weak conceptualization of the primary actors (the local and the international); (2) including an excessive focus on Western actors within the international; (3) a romanticized interpretation of hybrid peace governance structures; (4) a blindness towards the dominant role of local elites; an overstating of local resistance; and (4) an ambivalent relationship to practice. The author then asserts that the local turn in peacebuilding advocates for a major shift in focus from international peacebuilders to local people as the most important drivers of peace.

The local, however, in another conceptualization, is the everyday, ordinary individuals who live in villages and neighborhoods, or the “local-local” (Firchow, 2020). After all, it is the local actors that communicate the local needs of the community for peacebuilding and coordinate with the international actors especially in situations of conflict. The significance of the local is even more magnified when the state actors are absent at the local level to address situations of conflict. Hence, for the author, peace (and conflict, security, and development) is experienced and embodied at the local level. Local ownership of peacebuilding facilitates and supports local agency (Bojicic-Dzelilovic & Martin, 2016). This conceptualization recognizes that to include broad sections of the population and mobilizing local capacities is necessary for effective and sustainable interventions which better correspond to local needs and the changing local context. The authors also assert that the pursuit of local ownership implies building various types of partnerships which require time, commitment and funding that often go beyond the typical external aid frameworks. What is novel about this research is the concept of the whole of society approach, “whose perspective suggests that the promise of local ownership in international interventions is best served through identifying spaces of action within local society, and an adjustment of programming parameters to enable the UE to complement the efforts of domestic actors.”

In a more recent work from the same authors, using the whole of society (WOS) lens shows how current methods of engagement by the EU fail to embrace the diversity of the local society in pursuit of peacebuilding objectives (Bojicic-Dzelilovic & Martin, 2018). To quote at length, the WOS entails “that intervention practice can acknowledge and reflect local responses to conflicts not only by attempting to engage with a greater diversity of local stakeholders but also through identifying combinations of significant non-state actors, taking account of relationships and interactions among local groups, and by recognizing the breadth and relevance to indigenous practices.” For the authors, an inclusive WOS approach must include deeply embedded private businesses in the locality and the far-reaching influence of faith groups that institute adherence and social cohesion among social groups of diverse backgrounds. As a practice perspective, the WOS approach “enhances inclusivity and incorporates local agency but also in consideration of indigenous customs, cultures and responses to conflict which offer constructive entry points for engagement by external peacebuilders.”

Meaningful inclusivity, however, requires those with power to make space for those without (Donais & McCandless, 2017). The authors assert that inclusion requires that top-down, state-centric approaches must be complemented by bottom-up, society-centric processes. For them, inclusivity in the context of peacebuilding refers to “the carving out of space within which a cross-section of the conflict-affected community, from community-based organizations to ordinary citizens, to exercise meaningful voice and agency in the design and implementation of peace processes.” This conception of inclusivity opens a gateway for a host of actors within the triple nexus to come to the aid of conflict-affected areas, but at the same time allows for local actors with their indigenous means of peacebuilding at the grassroots level.

1.1.3 The Bangsamoro peace process

The Bangsamoro region has been characterized as being besieged by and ethno-nationalist (Liow, 2006) movement led by local *mujahideens* that either fight for autonomy (in the case of the Moro National Liberation Front) or independence (in the case of the Moro Islamic Liberation Front, except until recently in 2018, with the passage of the Republic Act 11054 or the Bangsamoro Basic Law that instituted the creation of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao). Identified causes of conflict in the Moro region are: (1) the longstanding pattern of inequality and injustice, (2) ancestral domain, (3) abject poverty (Ochiai, 2016), (4) structural inequalities in the socio-political and economic domains (Taya, 2010), (5) the government’s framework of asymmetric political autonomy in bureaucratic governance (Gera 2016), and (6) cultural differences and conflicting ‘imagined communities’ that have been neglected in terms of self-determination and cultural/religious emancipation (Stark, 2003).

A shortened version of the peace process is presented in its milestones is as follows: First, the signing of the 1976 Tripoli Agreement in Libya. The Agreement provided autonomy to the thirteen (13) provinces in the southern Philippines facilitated by Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) through the Libyan Government. Second, the passage of the Organic Act for the creation of the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao – the ARMM - (R.A. 6734) that included Sulu, Tawi-Tawi, Lanao del Sur and Maguindanao. Third, was the peace talks leading to the establishment of the Southern Philippines Council for Peace and Development (SPCPD) in 1996. Fourth, was the signing of the Tripoli agreement of Peace in Libya in 2001 that resulted in the Memorandum of Agreement on Ancestral Domain (MOA-AD) in 2008. Fifth, was the signing of the Framework Agreement on the Bangsamoro (FAB) in 2012 which finally concluded as the Comprehensive Agreement on the Bangsamoro (CAB) in 2014. And sixth, the Bangsamoro Basic Law (BBL) that paved the way for the Bangsamoro Transitional Authority (BTA) under the new Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). The Bangsamoro peace process has always been composed of these major players: the peace panel of the Government of the Republic of the Philippines (GRP), the recognized legitimate Moro leadership of both the MNLF and the MILF, along with and the presence of third-party negotiators or states. Multi-party peace negotiations such as the Bangsamoro peace process ensure that the parties would be bound by its signed commitments. The only factors that change in the scene are the players: with a change of administration every six years due to a constitutionally-mandated elections to replace the Presidency; the change of leadership, and recognition accorded to such change by the government, within the MNLF and the MILF; and the constitution of the third-party observers, mediators and facilitators that are multi-national in character, involving various experts, transnational Civil Society Organizations (CSOs),

international non-governmental organizations (INGOs), and national non-governmental organizations (NGOs). It is a plethora of state and non-state actors that are met on the ground by grassroots advocacy networks armed with, and constituted of, a humanitarian, peace, and development agenda.

1.2 Research Problem/ Questions

This paper is a humble attempt to investigate the heuristic and practical utility of the application of the vertical integration model of peacebuilding into the Bangsamoro peace process.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following queries:

1. How can the vertical integration model of peacebuilding be applied to the Bangsamoro peace process?
2. What international, national and local networks under the triple nexus work together in the Bangsamoro peace process?
3. What is local ownership of peacebuilding and what are its implications to the Bangsamoro peace process?

1.3 Theoretical Framework

1.3.1 Vertical Integration Model

Vertical integration refers to strategies that link actors, knowledge, and processes upwards across societal strata for improved peacebuilding and development impact (Gray & Burns, 2021). This perspective requires consensus-building among key stakeholders through participatory processes that do not deny agency or restrict alternative processes to achieve a desired end (Donais & McCandless, 2016). In addition, vertical relationships thus established may be across levels of governance (formal and informal) or across levels and scales (between individuals or non-state organizations to another government level or spatial scales) (Leonardsson, 2020). Moreover, vertical integration allows bottom-up processes to link with the top-down peacebuilding processes to ensure inclusivity (Donais & McCandless, 2016), where top-down, state-centric approaches must be complemented by bottom-up, society-centric strategies. Here, state-society relations (the vertical axis) must be fortified, as well as ensuring that inter-group relations (the horizontal axis) also remain intact to achieve effective and lasting peacebuilding

Central to the analysis of vertical relationships are the concepts of complementarity, autonomy, agency and context, as well as localization (Barakat & Milton, 2020) or otherwise also known as local ownership of peacebuilding. Hence the following are of equal importance: community-level dimensions of promoting post-conflict reconciliation (Clements & Lee, 2021) as a peacebuilding initiative, the interactions between national and local levels (Hancock & Mitchell, 2018) and the development of local peacebuilding models at local ownership (Lee, 2019), inclusive of its challenges in peacebuilding and conflict prevention (Bojicic-Dzelilovic & Martin, 2016).

Deep and appreciative dialogue is critical to peacebuilding and reconciliation (Clements & Lee, 2021). True reconciliation is where there is a meeting of truth, justice, peace and compassion; it involves a deep recognition of past wrongs, a request for forgiveness, the expression of apology and contrition; a willingness to make reparation, and a desire to celebrate differences. Here, promoting post-conflict reconciliation requires changes in individual attitudes and behavior but it also requires attention to the deeper structural and cultural sources of violence and non-violence. The authors stressed that peacebuilding and reconciliation processes are multilevel, multidimensional, and relationally transformative. In the communities effective dialogues for reconciliation (Abu-Nimer, 2021) should include the following key elements: (1) principle of trust, (2) purpose of learning, (3) interaction through proper communication channels, with an assumption of symmetry – that all members of the group are equal and have the same rights to expression and action, (4) ability to take risks, (5) the ability to engage with the other and with one's own faith group members, and (6) principle of action – the joint or unilateral action to illustrate commitment to reconciliation. These concepts and principles are of material significance to agency and context.

The relationship of grassroots actors to the goals of peacebuilding appears to be most intrinsic, in the sense that these actors typically engage in peacebuilding in order to achieve the goals of peacebuilding (Hancock & Mitchell, 2018). Peacebuilding initiatives of grassroots actors should be met with initiatives from the national government to achieve a common goal of fostering peace. Interactions with national and the local actors in the context of conflict should not be about the sense of legitimacy that one has over the other but should be a partnership of complementarity rather than that of rivalry. The four main areas of peacebuilding activities in Mindanao are: relief and protection, conflict resolution, peaceful coexistence, and rehabilitation and development (Lee, 2019). For relief and protection, many local peacebuilders pay attention to the establishment of zones of peace – geographic areas designated and declared by local communities as zones with no violence, hence conducive for peacebuilding. For conflict resolution, direct involvement in the ongoing peace process through consultation, policy proposals, monitoring and the like. For peaceful coexistence, programs have been instituted on various forms of peace education and advocacy as facilitated by a few local universities and grassroots organizations. And finally, for rehabilitation and development, programs have been instituted assisted by international aid agencies to pursue peace through development.

1.4 Significance of the study

This research is significant because it attempts to utilize the vertical integration framework into the Bangsamoro peace process. This allows a perspective to look at the peace process as a parallel process of the top-down and the bottom-up peacebuilding narratives vertically integrated through networks of the triple nexus.

2. Methodology

This paper has a qualitative research design using content analysis as its method. Hence, it is descriptive, and inferences are drawn from researches cited in this paper. The analysis is guided by the vertical integration model as its framework. This research was conducted at the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Data were drawn from the academic publications that are included in this paper and whose complete citation are reflected in the reference section. The analysis was guided by the framework and incorporated in the results and discussion section.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Vertical Integration and the Bangsamoro Peace Process

Sustainable peace can only be attained through cooperation, partnerships, and linkages along with the community's commitment to the pursuit of peace through the liberal-democratic framework. Here, the role of civil society is deemed critical. Civil society is defined to include a range of organizations – from development NGO's to church-based groups and business associations (Rood, 2005). Accordingly, these organizations pursue the achievement of peace through vital activities such as dialogue between communities, the provision of horizontal spaces for peace and their vertical involvement in peace policymaking (Rood, 2005). At the heart of these movements is the centrality of advocacy, grassroots peacebuilding and peacekeeping, advancement of the value of peace, and the provision of basic services, among others.

A selection and tabulation of information among thirty-nine (39) organizations (see table in the Appendices section) identified by peaceinsight.org as organizations and institutions that are in the pursuit of peace in Mindanao reveals that certain organizations, such as the MIDCOP Inc., “coordinates with non-state actors and state actors in partnership with The Asia Foundation (TAF), and the Department for International Development (DFID).” Another one is that of Move This World – Philippines, an affiliate of Move This World, Inc. based in New York, working on sustainable peacebuilding projects through “partnerships with teachers, schools and communities; sustained through a cost-sharing model.” Added to this is an organization cited by Rood (2005), the Initiatives for International Dialogue (IID) that nurtures international links to those organizations concerned with Mindanao issues. With these examples, the link between the local and the international has been established; where the obvious role of the state, other than peacebuilding policy legislation, is to support and facilitate these peacebuilding

initiatives by allowing them to take place in formal and informal contexts, serving as a conduit for access and legitimation. This makes the relationship between state, society and the international community critical to the pursuit of peace, and instrumental to the vertical integration model.

The core of a vertical integration model of peacebuilding is the realization that local agency of domestic actors is as equally important to that of the agency of international actors. The aim should be that *coherence and coordination* through partnerships and linkages that allows for vertical integration whether going up or going down the chain of relationships linking the international, the national, and the local in the context of peace building processes (Donais, n.d.).

The operationalization of vertical integration was extensively discussed by McCandless, Abitbol, and Donais (2015). According to the authors, the minimum conditions for vertical integration efforts to gain traction clearly includes the existence of political space and the willingness of the governments of fragile and conflict affected states to engage. However, beyond such minimum conditions, other priorities for putting vertical integration into practice include the following (to quote at great length):

1. Ensuring context and conflict sensitivity is the starting point for vertically integrating peacebuilding, and rejecting the imposition of models or approaches (especially those divorced from a robust analysis of socio-economic, security, and wider political dynamics);
2. Broadening and deepening the strategic lens with an eye towards more holistic engagement, bearing in mind the need for commitments and support that acknowledge the long-term nature of structural, normative, and relationship transformation;
3. Engaging with stakeholders representing diverse communities at all levels, especially those capable of facilitating broad national ownership of vertical integration processes, and supporting the development of inclusive participation processes and accountability structures to maintain this;
4. Developing strategy and programming rooted in clear and compelling theories of change, and links with wider peacebuilding and development strategic analyses and frameworks – national and international – to support and build linkages, both vertically and horizontally, across sectors, constituencies and efforts;
5. Identifying and addressing power asymmetries and abuses that undermine transformative peacebuilding; and
6. Reflecting critically on appropriate roles for different actors, with particular emphasis on the ways in which international actors can move away from social engineering and towards facilitating and ‘accompanying’ roles.

The Bangsamoro peace process, since its inception, reflects a multiplicity of actors that were involved in the mediation, facilitation, coordination and implementation of the successive agreements. Of value to the purposes of the present research is the International Monitoring Team (IMT), for the monitoring of the ceasefire and situations on the ground, and the International Contact Group (ICG) intended to serve as guarantor of negotiations for the Framework Agreement on the Bangsamoro. These two groups of international character included with them transnational civil society (TCS) organizations with local partnerships on the ground.

The International Monitoring Team (IMT) (Herbolzheimer, 2015) is comprised of 50 unarmed members of the armed forces of Malaysia, Libya and Brunei; and to include two officers of the Norwegian army with two experts from the European Union, plus a civilian protection component which included one international (the Nonviolent Peaceforce or NP) and three local NGOs [the Mindanao Human Rights Action Center (MinHRAC), the Mindanao People’s Caucus (MPC), and the Muslim Organization of Government and other Professionals (MOGOP)]. The NP is a global non-profit organization (NPO) protecting civilians in violent conflicts and building peace side-by-side with local communities (Nonviolent peaceforce, 2024). The MinHRAC has an extensive pool of local human rights actors drawn from various sectors because its partnership with the Consortium of Bangsamoro Civil Society (CBCS) allows it to work with Bangsamoro NGOs, People’s Organizations (POs) and other CSOs who have

committed themselves to a more sustainable advocacy for peace, human rights, good governance, and development (Peace insight, 2016). As such their groundwork for the advocacy on the ground parallel's that of the advocacy of the INGO Nonviolent Peace force creating a vertical integration across levels and scales (Leonardsson, 2020). Added to this network is the breadth of networks of its coordinating center, the Mindanao Dynamic Culture of Peace (MIDCOP Inc.). Accordingly, the MIDCOP Inc is a grassroots human rights advocacy group that conducts peace forums, partnerships in monitoring human rights violations, coordinates with non-state actors and state actors in partnership with the Asia Foundation (TAF) and the Department for International Development (DfID) (Peace insight, 2024). These linkages allow bottom-up processes of peacebuilding to link with the top-down peacebuilding processes, thereby ensuring inclusivity (Donais & McCandless, 2016). This also confirms the claim that peacebuilding and reconciliation processes are multilevel, multidimensional, and relationally transformative (Clements & Lee, 2021).

The International Contact Group (ICG) is the first-ever formal hybrid mediation support initiative of its kind (Democratic Progress Institute, 2014), composed of four third-party governments – The United Kingdom, Japan, Turkey, and Saudi Arabia - and four INGOs, accordingly, intended to serve as guarantor of negotiations (Hoffman, 2011). One of the NGOs in the ICG was Conciliation Resources, locally partnered with Teduray Lambangian Women's Organization Inc. (TLWOI), a federation of 35 community-based women's organization of indigenous peoples in the province of Maguindanao (Conciliation Resources, n.d.). The INGO Conciliation Resources has paved the way, with this partnership, for a network of local women's grassroots organizations to be able to meaningfully participate in the peace process from a bottom-up perspective. This is linked to the ground (top to bottom) by the International NGO itself through its available networks and resources.

The three other INGOs are Muhammadiyah (Indonesia), the Asia Foundation (USA), and the Center for Humanitarian Dialogue (Switzerland). These INGOs are specifically tasked to act as a bridge between parties, the facilitator, local partners, business and others; provide technical assistance to parties; and support communications for peace advocacy. However, their core challenge is to commit to confidentiality while advocating for inclusion and transparency (Democratic Progress Institute, 2014). Muhammadiyah is a major Islamic NGO in Indonesia with strong connections in civil infrastructure, particularly in the areas of health and education. It has an estimated 50 million affiliates (Monash University, 2018). This extensive connection provides a platform for grassroots Islamic organizations such as the local CBCS in the Philippines to have a voice in the peace process within and without the formal talks. In addition, quoting at length from the source, asserts that Muhammadiyah also convened multiple activities in Indonesia to increase social awareness and political support for the Mindanao peace process. They invited the MILF, GPH and ICG to peace events in Indonesia, where they provide health and educational services, and have done some bridging between the MILF and MNLF. Furthermore, the organization conducted exploratory visits to Mindanao to identify how best they can contribute with their expertise in human development (Democratic Progress Institute, 2014). On the other hand, The Asia Foundation (TAF) has a long-standing presence on the ground with partners from the private sector, the civil society, and government. With the TAFs partnership with MIDCOP Inc., the field coordinating office of MinHRAC, in support of grassroots-level human rights advocacy, makes their partnership determined to engage in peacebuilding in order to achieve the goals of peacebuilding (Hancock & Mitchell, 2018). The inflow of aid allows grassroots advocacy networks to constructively utilize these resources, gained through partnerships, for the attainment of common goals. Complementarity (Barakat & Milton, 2020) of desired goals is basic for vertical integration to occur. Hence, the goals on the ground of advocacy networks and CSOs must complement those that are already in place internationally and nationally.

3.2 Consensus-building through participatory processes

The object of any participatory process in peacebuilding is to reach a consensus, a common agreement as well as an understanding that the pursuit of peace is a much better alternative than addressing the aftermath of a conflict. Stakeholders must reach, at the very least, an overwhelming agreement that minimizes the loss of lives, the destruction of property, violation of human rights, as well as to ensure access to basic necessities (such as food and shelter, or personal security) even in situations of conflict. However, a consensus can only be reached if an

inclusive dialogue or forum has already been established that allows for the exchange of ideas and conversations, grounded on mutual respect and trust.

Participatory processes across levels of governance: the formal level happens at the level of the state, such as forums, dialogues, trainings; but at the same time these participatory processes also occur at the informal level, as women's groups and youth organizations contribute to peacebuilding at the grassroots level. Here, consensus building is an undertaking that stakeholders to the peace process engage in to effectively institutionalize lasting peace.

Participatory processes across levels and scales, that is between individuals or non-state actors and another government level. An example that can be cited here is that of *Kusog* Mindanao in 2001 (Rood, 2005) where, together with then President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo named an all-Mindanao peace panel with a civilian head (then presidential assistant for Mindanao Jesus Dureza), for an all "out-peace policy." *Kusog* Mindanao is an umbrella organization that has an NGO as its secretariat. This peace panel was participated in by civil society groups, business councils and elected public officials at that time.

To reach a consensus, one must be engaged in a dialogue. In post-conflict situations, the dialogue must center around the themes of reconciliation. However, the utility of conventional peacebuilding models for reconciliation would be unachievable without engaging with political authorities and the transformation of negative dynamics in state institutions (Clements & Lee, 2021). Accordingly, those who wish to advance reconciliation needs to pay more attention to the opportunities it creates for various social actors to participate in reconciliatory processes and to weave their own distinctive contributions into reconciliation design and implementation plans. Hence despite the presence of a multitude of grassroots advocating for peace and human rights, along with the presence of development workers, their effort would be in vain without facilitating the obvious need to sit down and talk between parties to a conflict, between and among victims, and mediating to reconcile the two.

3.2.1 Bottom-up processes to link with top-down peacebuilding

On one hand, bottom-up peacebuilding techniques have been utilized by civil society organizations to encourage understanding and improve inter-societal relations, such as inter-faith dialogues, continuing peace education, conflict resolution training, team-building activities, local community projects, and local advocacy campaigns among others. These activities aim at empowering individuals and local communities at the grassroots level to promote, as well as practice, *just* peace. On the other is top-down peacebuilding which puts emphasis on formal institutions in charge of conflict prevention, conflict management, and conflict resolution and transformation. Linking these two processes are networks of civil society organizations that work on both ends of this peacebuilding divide.

Conflict resolution and peacebuilding efforts by grassroots organizations and local civil society organizations are all essential for pushing forward the overall peace process (Trajano, 2020). NGOs and POs often form alliances, or cluster together in network organizations to acquire the advantages of scale, but this institutionalized collaboration also gives them the ability to have more impact. The author asserts that by forming an alliance or a network, these actors are able to gain more access to policymakers, facilitate collaboration among NGOs, provide leadership, and marshal support from elsewhere. In short, they become more visible. This research work is crucial in explaining why the NGOs of the IMT and the INGOs of the ICG have local partnerships with grassroots organizations. This serves as a two-way process: the INGOs can acquire local knowledge in facilitating and mediating situations of conflict through their networks on the ground, while those networks of advocates on the ground, get to have representation in a national and an international scene. Making them visible allows them to get and gain access to prospective donors who have a parallel mission and goal. Here, indigenous processes find recognition and utility with those working through peacebuilding from the top. This notion is summed up better in another research, positing that international assistance providers help address deficiencies in peacebuilding by providing technical and financial support but they have limited access, on the other hand, local CSOs have excellent context knowledge and access to conflict-affected locations but with limited financial resources and technical know-how (Gray & Burns, 2021), hence providing the link for bottom-up processes to link with top-

down peacebuilding. One must also be reminded that inclusion of civil society and the public (process inclusion) and their interests (content inclusion) is what underpins the inclusivity norm (Gray & Burns, 2021).

3.2.2 Networks and the Triple Nexus

This section identifies and discusses the international, national and local networks working within the Triple nexus in line with the Bangsamoro peace process.

For development NGOs, the “network of networks” in the Philippines is the Caucus of Development NGOs (CODE NGOs) – the largest organization of civil society in the country (Rood, 2005). Accordingly, this has a regional equivalent, the Mindanao Caucus of development NGO Networks (MinCODE) with 500 member organizations. For peace advocates, the Consortium of Bangsamoro Civil Society (CBCS) is a solidarity network of 40 Bangsamoro NGOs and other civil society organizations, together with its secretariat, the Kadtuntaya Foundation, Inc., is committed to an advocacy of sustainable peace, human rights, good governance, and development (see table Appendix on Civil Society and Other Organizations). For humanitarian

These organizations working in the triple nexus are vertically linked by organizations that seek principled partnerships between civil society organizations, local government units (LGUs) and international aid providers. Examples are that of MIDCOP Inc., with its partnership with the Asia Foundation and the Department for International Development; Balay Mindanao Foundation Inc. (BMFI) with its partnerships with LGUs, people’s organizations, NGOs and government agencies; and the Mindanao Peacebuilding Institute (MPI) that serves as a resource for peacebuilders as well as a training institute in the Asia Pacific that provides skills to individuals, institutions and communities that transcend the local, national and the international.

The Japanese government through the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), began its peacebuilding effort through the provision of development assistance to Mindanao in 2006 (Ishikawa, 2014). As a development agency, according to the author, JICA had three main departures from its mandate: (1) it decided to commence assistance under the cease-fire agreement even before a final peace agreement was signed between the GRP and the MILF, (2) since JICA worked under tremendous pressure due to the uncertainty of the peace process, it collaborated extremely well with all parties and agencies, (3) JICA supported peacemaking efforts by an innovative Track One-and-a-half mediation initiative after the peace process reached a stalemate in October 2008. The first mode of Japan’s assistance to Mindanao was the Task Force, consisting of the Embassy of Japan in the Philippines, JICA, and the Japan Bank for International Cooperation. The second mode was its participation in the IMT headed by Malaysia. The third mode was that of Japan-Bangsamoro Initiative for Reconstruction and Development (J-BIRD). It is in this mode that with its initial 12 grassroots programs, it expanded to technical cooperation, loan aid, and other relevant modalities of assistance aside from these programs. The Bangsamoro Development Authority served as the de facto partner of JICA for the Overseas Development Assistance (ODA) scheme. With the presence of JICA as partner for projects in the Bangsamoro, a network of state actors and non-state actors have mobilized themselves to work for the attainment of the goal of providing assistance to conflict-affected areas.

3.3 Local Ownership and its implications for the Bangsamoro peace process

Local ownership of peacebuilding simply means that local concerns as espoused by local agents must be at the core of any peacebuilding initiative. It must be the agents themselves or the local communities that identify and define the problem, but at the same time, provide solutions that are local as well. This method allows local agencies to be the central focus of peacebuilding, thereby allowing ownership of solutions provided for the problems thus identified. This makes peacebuilding sustainable because the solutions provided come from the locals themselves.

In this paper’s section on situating the local, a number of research have been reviewed. The local are at the frontlines of the humanitarian response to crisis situations (Barakat & Milton, 2021), because their local knowledge is appropriate to culture and context. Localization is primarily about empowerment and effectiveness. Though this conception points to a binary relationship (Mac Ginty, 2015), hence pushing for the local as a “de-territorialized,

networked and constituted by people and activity.” A notion that insists that the local is not a place, but is an activity constructed simultaneously by the local and the global. Therefore, the local turn in peacebuilding advocates for a major shift in focus from international peacebuilders to local people as the most important drivers of peace (Paffenholz, 2015). Nonetheless, it is the local actors that communicate the local needs of the community for peacebuilding and coordinate with the international actors especially in situations of conflict (Firchow, 2020). And because local ownership of peacebuilding facilitates and supports local agencies (Bojicic-Dzelilovic & Martin, 2016), indigenous and grassroots local knowledge of advocacy, peacebuilding and conflict resolution must be privileged. Recent research introduces the whole-of-society (WOS) approach (Bojicic-Dzelilovic & Martin, 2018) as “that intervention practice that can acknowledge and reflect local responses to conflicts not only by attempting to engage with a greater diversity of local stakeholders but also through identifying combinations of significant non-state actors, taking account of relationships and interactions among local groups, and by recognizing the breadth and relevance to indigenous practices.” It was also asserted that meaningful inclusivity requires those with power to make space for those without (Donais & McCandless, 2017).

The exercise of meaningful voice and agency in the design and implementation of peace processes is especially useful in the context of the Bangsamoro peace process because being multi-cultural by itself, does not allow for a unified approach to peace. The Maranaos have a way of resolving conflicts within and without through the practice of giving blood money for example, as a way of appeasing the aggrieved party, to avoid the escalation of a conflict. Another strategy is that of intermarriage, done through the marriage of one of the eligible bachelors or bachelorettes of the parties to a conflict, to ensure that the affinal family ties that bond would hold meaning and prevent bloodshed. Most often the parties to a conflict are called together for a dialogue by the respected elders of the community to ensure compliance to the terms of a peace agreement. These local/indigenous practices can inform the Bangsamoro peace process that there are other means of resolving conflicts other than the top-down or the bottom-up processes. The peace process can be indigenous, utilizing indigenous practices and can be down to the grassroots level through the assistance of local community elders that still hold significant influence over the behavior of the community-at-large.

4. Conclusion

First, the vertical integration model can be applied to the Bangsamoro peace process through an inspection of the actors involved in the process, from mediation to facilitation to implementation. The network of actors from top-down peacebuilding narrative complements as well as facilitate the bottom-up peacebuilding narratives of advocates and actors on the ground be they from the humanitarian, peace, or development sectors. The triple nexus allows the vertical integration of peacebuilding through networks and partnerships that transcend the local, the national and the international.

Second, multiple actors, facilitated by governments and mobilized by development aid work under the triple nexus as partners in the fostering of peace initiatives in the Bangsamoro region. Donor agencies, foreign governments and local networks of CSOs, in partnership with TCS organizations, are working to observe, mediate, and facilitate peace. This can only be made possible with the liberal project that entails cooperation, coordination, and collaboration based on mutual trust and a multitude of other factors.

Third, the local turn though contested in some ways, informs the Bangsamoro peace process that there are many ways that one to resolve conflict. Participation and accommodation are just features of the process, what matters most is the realization that possible solutions to the still ongoing Bangsamoro peace process may just be around the corner, through indigenous processes already known to the locals themselves.

5. Implications

First, peacebuilding through networks transcends the silos of the triple nexus and enhances the facilitation of peace processes on the ground. The nexus is merely an academic terminology to facilitate a discussion of the compartmentalization of advocacy networks that are working on the clock to foster peace. On the ground, the

nexus, unless threatened by security concerns, merely serves as an identification of the advocacy agenda of the actor immersed in relevant communities at stake.

Second, the agenda of TCS, CSOs, POs and other advocacy groups is not made at the outset, but rather reflected in the kind of work and the impact they make in the communities where they work. After all, peace advocates, development workers and humanitarian actors are all affected by security concerns – security of the individual in cases of armed confrontations. Hence, all must work together albeit knowing that their advocacies are complementary to each other.

Finally, literature on the local is fairly new. The contestations therein are academicians and practitioners trying to establish a niche in the field, hence clearly explaining the logic of their intellectual arrogance. And yet, whether the local is a place or an activity, does not actually matter. All that matters is a clear vision of what to address and how.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

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